

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Sheraton Moon Hotel: A Rigorous Design in Dynamic Huzhou

Adjei Isaac ^{1*}, Yang Ziqi ¹, Ahiave Seyram Edem², Sylla Mamadama², Soumah Aminata², Diallo Fatoumata Diaraye Ousmane²

¹Department of Environmental Design, Huzhou Normal University, China

²Department of Visual Art Design, Huzhou Normal University, China

Accepted

January 29,2022

Published

February 06,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s);

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

*Corresponding Author: Adjei Isaac

Funding: No

How to cite this article (APA): Adjei, I., Yang, Z., Ahiave, S. E., Sylla, M., Soumah, A., Diallo, F. D. O. (2022). Sheraton Moon Hotel: A Rigorous Design in Dynamic Huzhou. *North American Academic Research*, 5(1), 108-114. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5979547>

ABSTRACT

This study highlights the rigorous design of the Sheraton Moon Hotel of Huzhou city in the People's Republic of China. It was designed by architect Ma Yansong by MAD Architects and built by Shanghai Feizhou Group. It is the first five-star hotel in mainland China for the prosperous and influential "business class", oozing wealth and extravagance. Its construction took about 6 years that is from 2007 to 2013. This rigorous design has contributed immensely to the beautiful China and dynamic Huzhou agenda. The study reveals the design concepts, structural design and several specifications of the skyscraper. Its designer, architect Ma Yansong states that the shape is inspired by traditional bridges represented in ancient Chinese paintings. Throughout Chinese history, people have always sought a harmonious relationship with nature and this has become an important part of Chinese culture and tradition. Huzhou is a famous place for traditional ink paintings and splendid views of the water and the arch bridge is one of the key elements of traditional architecture.

Keywords

Huzhou City, Sheraton moon hotel, Tai Lake, China

Introduction

Huzhou is a prefecture-level city located in northern Zhejiang Province. The city borders Jiaxing to the east and Hangzhou to the south. In 2017, the city's GDP grew by 8.5% Y-o-Y, marking it the second fastest growing city in Zhejiang Province. The city's major industries include textiles, wood flooring, electronic equipment and machinery, and chemical products. Situated at the heart of the Yangtze River Delta, Huzhou lies just 75km from Hangzhou and Jiaxing, 130km from Shanghai and 220km from Nanjing. Four major

expressways pass through the city, enabling access to major YRD cities (e.g., Shanghai, Hangzhou, Suzhou, Jiaxing, and Nanjing). As such, Huzhou is well positioned for regional distribution in the YRD region.

Due to its close proximity to Hangzhou, Huzhou has benefited from the growth of one of the most dynamic cities in China, which is also the headquarters of China's e-commerce giant Alibaba. According to the YRD Development Plan ratified by the State Council in 2016, Huzhou, together with Jiaxing and Shaoxing, are included in the "Hangzhou Metropolitan Area". The regional-planning initiative aims to integrate Hangzhou's development with the three northern Zhejiang cities ([wikiarquitectura, 2018](#)). They will cooperate in various areas, including transportation connectivity, cross-border e-commerce, innovation and information technology, etc. Vibrant local consumption and active e-commerce and 3PL demand have underpinned demand for Class A warehouses in the YRD region. As most cities in the YRD region are experiencing supply constraints, Huzhou will benefit from low vacancy rates in other major logistics hub cities, especially Hangzhou, Jiaxing and Shanghai.

The Sheraton Moon Hotel

The Sheraton Huzhou Hot Spring Resort (浙江湖州喜来登温泉度假酒店), also known as Moon Hotel is a spacious luxury resort located in Huzhou, China. It has nicknames such as "Horseshoe Hotel" and "Doughnut Hotel". It was designed by architect Ma Yansong by MAD Architects and built by Shanghai Feizhou Group. It is the first five-star hotel in mainland China for the prosperous and influential "business class", oozing wealth and extravagance. The Sheraton Moon Tai Lake Resort hotel is located next to Nan Tai Lake in Huzhou, a city situated west of Shanghai and north of Hangzhou, with views to Suzhou and Wuxi across the lake. Since ancient times, Huzhou has been known as "the house of silk" and "the land of plenty," and is the only ancient cultural city in the Nan Tai Lake region. The hotel connects with this local context, referencing both traditional and modern conditions, and is iconic in its integration and reflective dialogue with the waterscape of Tai Lake. The Moon Hotel takes full advantage of its waterfront by directly integrating architecture and nature. The circular building corresponds with its reflection in the water, creating a surreal image and mutable connection between solid reality and an aquatic phantom. Beneath the sunlight and the reflection of the lake, the curved shape of the building is crystal clear. When night falls, the entire building is brightly illuminated by both its interior and exterior lighting. Soft light wraps around the hotel and the water, resembling the bright moon rising above the lake, blending classical China and modern China in an interlocking embrace

Figure 1&2: Day and night view of the Sheraton moon hotel

Materials and methods

Design Concept

The design is based on the idea of unity and infinity. At night, the ring, which is a complete oval attached at the bottom by two underground levels, reflected in the lake and looks like a full moon glow. Its designer, architect Ma Yansong states that the shape is inspired by traditional bridges represented in ancient Chinese paintings. Throughout Chinese history, people have always sought a harmonious relationship with nature and this has become an important part of Chinese culture and tradition. Huzhou is a famous place for traditional ink paintings and splendid views of the water and the arch bridge is one of the key elements of traditional architecture. The Moon Hotel, as it is also known, uses its location through direct integration of architecture and nature. The circular building reflected in water creates a surreal picture, a connection between the real and the spooky. Under the sunlight and the reflection of the lake, the curved shape of the building is crystal clear. When night falls, the whole building glows, lighting both inside as on the outside. The soft light wraps around the water and the hotel, and the result resembles the bright moon rising over the lake, a classical and modern mixture through reflection. The Hotel Luna emphasizes the harmony of man with nature, trying to enhance the sensual and spiritual experiences of visitors, trying to become a new symbol of the relationship between humanity and nature.

Structural Design

From the beginning, designing an inhabitable vertical glass ring posed a great challenge for the structural engineers. It was eventually decided that a reinforced concrete-core tube would be most lightweight, most capable of containing a dense program, and most earthquake-resistant. However, it was also a challenge to implement a concrete structure and meet the goal of reducing environmental pollution during construction. The mesh-covered, curved surface structure gives the building its necessary rigidity, which is further enhanced by the bridge-like bracing steel structure that connects with the double-cone structure at the top floor. The hotel façade is covered with layers of fine-textured white aluminum rings and glass, creating a sense of drama and ambiguity around the building's scale. The Sheraton Huzhou Hot Spring Resort has a matching pair of

27-story towers that connect at higher levels to form a gently curved arc across the water. In the underground portion is attached by two levels of basements. The mesh structure of curved surface makes it more solid building strength and this is reinforced by the steel structure shaped bridge connecting the double cone structure on the top floor. The facade of the hotel is covered with layers of white aluminum rings and fine textured glass, producing the illusion and drama of the scale of the building.

The thin shape of the structure allows for maximal ventilation to the various rooms and suites. Each floor also has open-air terraces, shielding the interior from direct sunlight during the summer, while allowing for sunlight to penetrate the interior during winter. It is common to see people enjoying the sunlight warmth from their balconies during the summer. The outdoor space at the top of the structure acts to supplant the footprint at the ground by providing a roof garden for the enjoyment of guests. The annular shape of the hotel provides all rooms with favorable views of the waterfront and surrounding city, while allowing for maximal natural light in all directions. The arc-like public space at the top of the building has great open views and acts as a “mid-air” multi-purpose room for large-scale activities (archipanic, 2013). The experience of being at the top invokes a feeling of floating over the lake. Through all of these gestures, the Moon Hotel emphasizes the harmony between man and nature, and enhances visitors' sensual and spiritual experiences. It stands as Huzhou's new symbol of the connection between humanity and nature, past, present and future.

Figure 3&4: Floor plan and elevation of the hotel

Materials

The resort is richly decorated inside, its walls covered with different types of Jade and ceiling covered with European glass lamps are big waves formed with 20,000 Swarovski crystals lobby while the floor is paved with Afghan Jade and White Eye of Trigre Brazil. The luxurious resort features porches and ceilings inlaid with Citrine, a type of jade symbolizing wealth, while the reddish type cryolite or Silk Road is used as decoration on some fronts and on the desks of the janitors. Although the decor is unashamedly extravagant resort, some efforts were made to reduce the power consumption of the project.

Facades

According to the [Council on Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat, \(2013\)](#) Unlike conventional facades created with glass curtain wall, frequently in the design of hotels, the Sheraton Huzhou not require the installation of a large number of air conditioning units. The shape of the building gives shade to all balconies and promotes natural ventilation. The ultra-white glass allows natural light in all rooms, eliminating the need for additional artificial lighting during the day. This saves energy and creates a pleasant atmosphere. During the evening light LED accessories enliven the facade round, showing textures and colorful patterns that are reflected in the water surface.

Figure 5&6: Illustration of the Facades

Spaces

The hotel is actually a complete oval, two underground levels connect the visible shape of a horseshoe. The annular shape of the hotel allows all rooms to have good views and natural light from all directions. The public space in an arc at the top with open views, acts as a “place in the air,” creating the sensation of floating on the lake, dedicated to large-scale activities.

Rooms

The hotel, in its 27 floors offers 321 rooms, including 44 suites and 39 villas, all with private balconies. The bathrooms are covered in marble, including a sunken tub and oversized shower with rainforest shower. Inside buildings forming the complex there is a separate ‘spa town’ that has 8 villas, 40 hot springs and a dock for yachts. The resort has a club for guests, a ballroom and a variety of restaurants and bars.

Figure 7&8: Elegant views of the hotel room

Recreational Spaces

The many facilities the hotel offers a modern fitness center that includes high-tech machines, cardiovascular equipment, stretching areas, indoor and outdoor. Spa facilities include a steam room, saunas and a hydrotherapy tub in each locker room.

Figure 9. Modern Fitness Center.

Commercial facilities and events

The resort offers 16 meeting spaces, equipped with the latest technology, from high-speed internet, translation services, secretarial services, ATM, cell phone rental and any other requirements necessary for national and international transactions. The rooms, the largest with 902 m² (The Grand Ballroom), can also be used for different events, meetings or conferences. An island of 1.600m² is dedicated to wedding receptions. In the 22nd floor several private meeting rooms are located and in 27, the multipurpose room offers a splendid view of Taihu Lake.

Figure 10&11: Conference room and wedding reception

Conclusion

Through all of these gestures, the Moon Hotel emphasizes the harmony between man and nature, and enhances visitors' sensual and spiritual experiences. It stands as Huzhou's new symbol of the connection between

humanity and nature, past, present and future. This is a rigorous design which has contributed so much to the dynamism and beautification of Huzhou city and China as a great nation in the world as far as environmental aesthetics is concerned.

References

- [1] Wikiarquitectura, 2018. Retrieved from <https://en.wikiarquitectura.com/building/sheraton-huzhou-hot-spring-resort/#> accessed on 2021/02/18
- [2] Archipanic, 2013. Retrieved from <https://www.archipanic.com/sheraton-moon-hotel/> accessed on 2021/02/23
- [3] Council on Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat, 2013. Retrieved from <https://www.skyscrapercenter.com/building/sheraton-huzhou-hot-spring-resort/15527#tab-about> accessed on 2021/03/02

Author's Name: Adjei Isaac

Author's Email: nanaadjei130@mail.com

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

